

Productivity Growth of Indian Housing Sector Companies: Using Malmquist Productivity Index

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Abstract: Productivity affects the competitiveness of Business organizations and evaluating productivity improvement of the Decision-making Units (DMUs) is essential for the proper planning and effective performance of these units. This paper explores the overall productivity aspect of Indian Housing companies from 2010 to 2019. Malmquist Productivity Index is used to measure the productivity growth of each firm. The findings revealed that there was an overall rise in productivity in 2010-11, 2015-16 and 2018-19 only; however, there was a reduction in productivity during remaining years of the study period. Technological deterioration can be considered as the key cause of this decline. Thus, productivity growth can be accomplished through technological development and optimum utilization of inputs.

Keywords: Productivity, Housing, Malmquist Productivity, Data Envelopment Analysis.

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INTRODUCTION:

The Indian Housing sector had gone through colossal changes since the past. It plays a prominent part in the nation's employment and production productivity. The demand for homes is ceaselessly expanding with fast urbanization and high earnings. The developers are concocting innovative methods to tap the changing requirements of the home purchasers. The sector was especially affected by demonetization, RERA Act, 2016 and GST (Thornton, 2019).

The productivity performance determines the Wealth of Nations (Smith, 1776). Performance appraisal is a significant tool for companies to be competitive and has a vital role to play in a growing market with increasing competition. Evaluating the performance and setting benchmarks has a positive effect on companies to grow steadily and improve themselves to exist and thrive in a globally competitive environment. The objective of this study is to evaluate the

performance of Housing sector companies in terms of total factor productivity. The overall change in factor productivity is split into two key components, namely technological change and technical change. Decision-making units (DMUs) can achieve greater economic success through refinements in technology and technical efficiency and thereby can acquire greater strategic strength. In this way, the enhancement in the technical efficiency is taken as an indicator of DMUs for the adaption of global technologies and thus shows the “catch up” portion of the overall productivity. The Malmquist index is used to measure the productivity growth of the housing sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Fare et al (1995) computed the productivity of manufacturing industries in Taiwan by using the radial Malmquist index. The authors decompose productivity into efficiency change and technical change. The study found that improvements in productivity were because of technical progress and it was higher during the liberalization period. **Murillo-Melchor (1999)** used the Malmquist Index to evaluate the efficiency and productivity changes in the Airports of Spain. The results concluded that the sector had suffered a huge reduction in efficiency during 1993, however, showed slight progress in 1994. **Asmild et al (2004)** dealt with the issue of “same period frontier” in Window Analysis and Malmquist Index. It recommends that window analysis and Malmquist index when used independently give appropriate outcomes. However, using DEA window-based Malmquist does not give accurate results of decomposition into catching up and frontier shift effects. **Candemir and Deliktas (2007)** used Data envelopment analysis (DEA) to assess the effectiveness and productivity growth of Turkish Agricultural Firms and performed regression to know the impacts of different factors affecting the production efficiencies of the firms. The results concluded that productivity growth diminished by 1.2 per cent because of 2.7 per cent technical deterioration. **Empouznejad and Thanassoulis (2010)** introduced the Dynamic Malmquist model to evaluate the productivity Index. It compares the results of Static and Dynamic Malmquist model and concludes that the dynamic efficiency results for OECD nations ought to reflect reality better than those dependent on the conventional models. **Jreisat and Paul (2010)** had measured the effectiveness and productivity of Jordanian Banking sector. It used an input-oriented VRS model to assess the efficiency scores and Malmquist Index to assess the productivity change. It concluded that the small-sized banks are more proficient than the medium-sized banks. **Candemir (2011)** examined the productivity improvements of Hazelnut

Agricultural Sales Cooperatives Unions (HASCOS) in Turkey using Data Envelopment Analysis and Malmquist Index. The results showed that efficiency scores range from 0.841 to 0.938. **Abdel-Wahab and Vogl (2011)** compared the productivity performance of the construction industry with other industries in the UK, US, Japan and Europe. The analysis concluded that labour productivity had shown a downfall in construction as well as in other industries. **Elshakour (2012)** identified the set of key performance indicators that can be used to evaluate the performance of the Construction industry. It suggested that other performance indicators such as customer satisfaction, planning effectiveness and safety should be used besides the traditional financial indicators. **Sanchez (2018)** provided a new DEA model that conquers the shortcomings of traditional Malmquist Index and Window analysis. An incredible feature of the new model is that it offers verifiable information regarding time, which was a shortcoming in the traditional Malmquist model that assesses change of productivity just in two periods. **Jreisat (2018)** employed input-oriented Malmquist Index to examine the total factor productivity growth of 10 Australian Real Estate Investment Trusts (AREITs). The results demonstrate that the average efficiency declined and innovation relapsed from 2004 to 2011. Apparently, the typical REIT had failed to progress technically, however applying aggressive growth techniques can help to find the best practice to operate. **Malhotra and Dhandra (2020)** measured the technical efficiency and productivity of Indian Housing companies from 2008 to 2017. The findings showed a minimal increase in the performance of the companies. The research indicated the need for technical innovation among firms.

Various approaches related to the measurement of total factor productivity appear in the literature. Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is one of the most widely used techniques. As far as the literature is studied, the housing sector has rarely been investigated from the perspective of productivity in the context of India. In this research, the Malmquist Index of Data Envelopment analysis is used to calculate the productivity of housing companies over the period 2010 to 2019. This research can make an enormous contribution to the literature by providing information on the productivity of the housing sector companies of India.

DATA AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sources of Data

Data on the financial variables used in the analysis were obtained from the annual reports of the sample companies and from CAPITALINE database.

Sample Selection

Housing sector companies listed on Bombay stock exchange have been selected for the study. The selection of the companies is based on annual turnover and companies with an annual turnover of 2.5 billion or above have been selected for the analysis. Inputs and Outputs were selected based on previous researches. Three inputs are Gross Assets, Material Cost, Employee Cost and the output is Total revenue. The following firms are included in the sample on the basis of an average annual turnover of the last ten years.

Table1: Sample Profile

Name of the Company	BSE Code	Average Annual Turnover (in Billion)
DLF Ltd.	DLF	30.06
Sobha Ltd	SOBHA	20.22
Prestige Estates Projects Ltd	PRESTIGE	19.92
Unitech Ltd	UNITECH	15.57
Housing Development & Infrastructure Ltd	HDIL	9.84
Ansal Properties	ANSALAPI	8.22
Oberoi Realty Ltd.	OBEROIRLTY	6.82
Parsvnath Developers Ltd	PARSVNATH	5.23
Vascon Engineers Ltd	VASCONEQ	4.32
Ansal Housing	ANSALHSG	3.77
Vipul Ltd.	VIPUL	2.85

Notes: This table shows the details of the sample firms such as name, BSE code and average annual Turnover

Methodology

In this article, the Malmquist Index was used for evaluating the contribution of technical efficiency change and technological improvements in productivity. Fare et al (1994) described growth in productivity as a result of improvement in production and technological changes. Malmquist (1953) first introduced the concept of Malmquist Index and then various scholars later researched and made improvements in it {Caves et.al (1982); Fare

et.al (1989), (1994); Fare, Grosskopf & Russell (1998); Fare & Grosskopf (1992); Thrall (2000)}.

INTERPRETATIONS AND FINDINGS

Table 2 provides detailed results for individual changes and their supporting elements for each time period. For the year 2010-11, the average total factor productivity change is 5.8 per cent ($1.058-1=0.058*100=5.8\%$). In the case of DLF, the total factor productivity was 36.3 per cent ($1.363-1.00=0.36*100=36.3\%$) which was higher when compared to other firms. This is due to an increase in technological change to the extent of 36.3 per cent. From 2011-12, only 3 firms showed growth in total factor productivity. For Ansal Housing and Parsvnath, the productivity progress was due to improvement in the performance of technical efficiency, which resulted from an improvement in scale efficiency. Oberoi Realty had higher productivity of 28.3 per cent ($1.283-1.00=0.283*100=28.3\%$) while comparing to the other firms.

In 2012-13, Prestige ltd. and Sobha had a productivity rise of 9.9 per cent and 3.2 per cent respectively. Both companies had improved productivity due to an improvement in technical efficiency. The technical performance of Prestige ltd. increased by 35.9 per cent and of Sobha by 26 per cent. The average productivity decline is 3.6 per cent, which is a result of technological regress. During 2013-14, Ansal Housing, Ansal properties and Prestige Ltd had productivity improvement because of technical efficiency change. However, the growth in Parsvnath was due to technological enhancement. Prestige ltd had the highest productivity of 13.4 per cent during this period. Sobha Ltd. had shown the stagnant position; it neither showed progress nor regress. Vipul Ltd. had shown the highest fall in productivity (20.7 per cent). The average change in productivity growth was -5.1 per cent.

During 2014-15, Ansal Housing, DLF and HDIL had improvement in their productivity. Ansal housing had the highest growth of 12.5 per cent followed by HDIL with 6.4 per cent and DLF with 0.9 per cent respectively. The improvement in productivity was because of technological change. Remaining 8 firms (Ansal Properties, Oberoi Realty, Parsvnath, Prestige, Sobha, Unitech, Vascon Engineers and Vipul ltd.) suffered productivity decline. This decline mostly arises due to technological regress in these firms. During the whole time frame, technical efficiency of 4 firms (DLF, HDIL, Oberoi Realty and Unitech) remained the same, causing no effect to the productivity change.

From 2015 to 2016, all firms except Oberoi Realty had positive technological change. DLF had stable technical efficiency. Prestige Ltd. had shown the highest productivity growth of 96.5 per cent during this period. However, Ansal housing suffered a 20.4 per cent productivity decline. The average productivity growth for 2015-16 was 17.1 per cent. For 2016-17, 2 firms (Ansal housing and Vascon Engineers) demonstrated positive total factor productivity. This can be directly attributed to technical change. During this time frame, all the firms suffered technological deterioration. Prestige Ltd. had the highest downfall in the productivity i.e., 46 per cent decline.

During 2017-18, 3 firms (Ansal Housing, Oberoi Realty and Vipul ltd., the improvement in productivity were due to technological change only, their technical efficiency remained same causing no impact on productivity change. Ansal Properties, DLF, and HDIL also saw no change in their technical efficiency, but their overall productivity decline due to technological deterioration. Prestige Ltd. and Unitech both suffered from negative technical efficiency and technological deterioration, due to which their overall productivity also decline by 17.9 per cent and 10.3 per cent simultaneously.

Throughout 2018-19, 8 firms (Ansal Housing, Ansal Properties, HDIL, Oberoi Realty, Prestige Ltd., Sobha, Unitech and Vascon Engineers) had productivity growth. The productivity in 4 out of 8 firms was due to technological improvement, while their technical efficiency remained the same because of no change in scale efficiency and input utilization. However, the productivity in another 4 firms (Ansal Housing, Sobha, Unitech and Vascon Engineers) was because of positive technical change. Ansal properties had shown the highest productivity growth of 33.5 per cent, however, Parsvnath had shown the highest productivity decline by 23.2 per cent. The overall average productivity increased by only 0.2 per cent during this period.

Table 2: Malmquist Index Results (Large)

DMUs	2010-2011					2011-2012					2012-2013				
	Effch	Techch	Pech	Sech	Tfpch	Effch	Techch	Pech	Sech	Tfpch	Effch	Techch	Pech	Sech	Tfpch
ANSALHSG	0.986	1.037	1.000	0.986	1.022	1.170	0.879	1.000	1.170	1.029	1.096	0.891	0.978	1.121	0.977
ANSALAPI	0.917	1.005	0.912	1.005	0.922	1.094	0.844	0.943	1.160	0.923	0.994	0.961	1.061	0.937	0.955
DLF	1.000	1.363	1.000	1.000	1.363	1.000	0.991	1.000	1.000	0.991	1.000	0.993	1.000	1.000	0.993
HDIL	1.000	1.052	1.000	1.000	1.052	1.000	0.655	1.000	1.000	0.655	1.000	0.937	1.000	1.000	0.937
OBEROIRLTY	0.906	1.149	1.000	0.906	1.041	1.104	1.162	1.000	1.104	1.283	0.862	1.100	1.000	0.862	0.948
PARSVNATH	0.927	1.055	1.022	0.907	0.978	1.083	0.946	0.999	1.083	1.024	1.180	0.839	1.305	0.904	0.990
PRESTIGE	0.949	1.130	0.973	0.975	1.072	0.779	0.890	0.843	0.925	0.693	1.359	0.808	1.087	1.251	1.099
SOBHA	0.881	1.151	0.903	0.976	1.014	1.173	0.839	1.089	1.077	0.984	1.260	0.819	1.245	1.012	1.032
UNITECH	1.000	1.079	1.000	1.000	1.079	1.000	0.729	1.000	1.000	0.729	1.000	0.998	1.000	1.000	0.998
VASCONEQ	1.054	0.913	0.970	1.087	0.962	1.070	0.732	1.239	0.864	0.784	0.937	0.932	1.017	0.921	0.873
VIPUL	1.124	1.060	1.000	1.124	1.191	1.048	0.891	1.000	1.048	0.934	1.000	0.833	1.000	1.000	0.833
MEAN	0.974	1.085	0.979	0.995	1.058	1.042	0.859	1.006	1.035	0.895	1.054	0.915	1.058	0.996	0.964

DMUs	2013-2014					2014-2015					2015-2016				
	Effch	Techch	Pech	Sech	Tfpch	Effch	Techch	Pech	Sech	Tfpch	Effch	Techch	Pech	Sech	Tfpch
ANSALHSG	1.314	0.806	0.960	1.368	1.059	0.841	1.338	1.051	0.800	1.125	0.672	1.185	0.794	0.847	0.796
ANSALAPI	1.368	0.737	1.268	1.080	1.009	0.653	1.250	0.817	0.799	0.816	1.370	1.225	1.258	1.089	1.678
DLF	1.000	0.795	1.000	1.000	0.795	1.000	1.009	1.000	1.000	1.009	1.000	1.145	1.000	1.000	1.145
HDIL	1.000	0.939	1.000	1.000	0.939	1.000	1.064	1.000	1.000	1.064	0.986	1.036	1.000	0.986	1.021
OBEROIRLTY	1.160	0.825	1.000	1.160	0.957	1.000	0.963	1.000	1.000	0.963	0.997	0.914	1.000	0.997	0.911
PARSVNATH	0.942	1.075	1.024	0.920	1.012	0.912	1.018	0.852	1.070	0.928	0.906	1.348	1.146	0.791	1.222
PRESTIGE	1.162	0.976	1.502	0.773	1.134	0.889	0.932	0.892	0.997	0.828	1.459	1.347	1.121	1.301	1.965
SOBHA	0.887	1.128	1.457	0.608	1.000	1.077	0.897	1.000	1.077	0.967	0.980	1.118	0.635	1.544	1.095
UNITECH	1.000	0.871	1.000	1.000	0.871	1.000	0.861	1.000	1.000	0.861	0.964	1.062	0.972	0.992	1.024
VASCONEQ	0.895	1.037	0.931	0.961	0.928	0.800	0.895	0.866	0.924	0.716	1.262	1.208	1.348	0.936	1.525
VIPUL	0.907	0.874	1.000	0.907	0.793	1.102	0.885	1.000	1.102	0.976	0.823	1.177	1.000	0.823	0.969
MEAN	1.046	0.907	1.088	0.961	0.949	0.925	1.000	0.949	0.974	0.925	1.015	1.154	1.006	1.009	1.171

DMUs	2016-2017					2017-2018					2018-2019				
	Effch	Techch	Pech	Sech	Tfpch	Effch	Techch	Pech	Sech	Tfpch	Effch	Techch	Pech	Sech	Tfpch
ANSALHSG	1.446	0.698	1.275	1.135	1.009	1.187	0.903	1.000	1.187	1.072	1.079	0.988	1.000	1.079	1.066
ANSALAPI	1.313	0.632	1.135	1.157	0.830	1.000	0.961	1.000	1.000	0.961	1.000	1.335	1.000	1.000	1.335
DLF	1.000	0.660	1.000	1.000	0.660	1.000	0.766	1.000	1.000	0.766	0.834	1.092	1.000	0.834	0.911
HDIL	1.015	0.690	1.000	1.015	0.700	1.000	0.889	1.000	1.000	0.889	1.000	1.073	1.000	1.000	1.073
OBEROIRLTY	1.003	0.798	1.000	1.003	0.800	1.000	1.177	1.000	1.000	1.177	1.000	1.147	1.000	1.000	1.147
PARSVNATH	1.225	0.741	0.952	1.286	0.908	0.766	1.028	0.717	1.068	0.787	0.730	0.998	1.286	0.567	0.728
PRESTIGE	0.907	0.617	1.000	0.907	0.560	0.947	0.867	1.000	0.947	0.821	1.000	1.008	1.000	1.000	1.008
SOBHA	1.386	0.713	1.576	0.880	0.989	1.074	0.899	1.000	1.074	0.966	1.023	0.996	1.000	1.023	1.019
UNITECH	1.037	0.816	1.029	1.008	0.846	0.901	0.995	1.000	0.901	0.897	1.037	0.985	1.000	1.037	1.021
VASCONEQ	1.436	0.702	1.147	1.253	1.008	1.102	0.906	0.859	1.283	0.998	1.012	0.991	0.975	1.037	1.002
VIPUL	1.215	0.813	1.000	1.215	0.988	1.000	1.272	1.000	1.000	1.272	1.000	0.840	1.000	1.000	0.840
MEAN	1.165	0.713	1.089	1.070	0.831	0.992	0.960	0.957	1.037	0.953	0.969	1.035	1.021	0.949	1.002

Notes: This table provides the results from the Malmquist Index which shows the change in efficiency from 2008 to 2009, 2009 to 2010, 2010 to 2011, 2011 to 2012, 2012 to 2013, 2013 to 2014, 2014 to 2015, 2015 to 2016 and 2016 to 2017. The scores represent the changes in technical efficiency (effch), technological efficiency (techch), pure technical efficiency (pech), scale expansion (sech) and total factor productivity (tfpch).

Figure 1: Results of Malmquist

Figure 1 shows the outcome of the Malmquist Index that is the product of “catch up effect” and “Frontier Shift”. It presents the effects of the overall productivity of individual firms. Highest improvements were made during 2015-16 as Prestige estates, Ansal Properties and Vascon Engineers demonstrated significant technological progress. Since 2016-17, most firms had an average rise in productivity.

Table 3: Summary of Malmquist Index Results

Year	Productivity growth	Productivity regress	Technological improvement	Technological deterioration	Efficiency improvement	Efficiency decline
2 2010-11	8	3	10	1	2	6
3 2011-12	3	8	1	10	7	1
4 2012-13	2	9	1	10	4	3
5 2013-14	4	6	3	8	4	4
6 2014-15	3	8	5	6	2	5
7 2015-16	8	3	3	9	4	8
8 2016-17	2	9	0	11	9	1
9 2017-18	3	8	3	8	3	3
10 2018-19	8	3	5	6	4	2

Notes: This table represents the number of firms from the sample which showed an increase or decrease in productivity, the number of firms which showed technological improvement or deterioration and the number of firms that showed the efficiency improvement or decline.

As presented in Table 3, Malmquist results revealed that the number of companies with productivity growth was eight in the 2nd year of analysis. The increase in productivity was primarily due to technological advances (10 out of 11 firms had shown technological progress).

Furthermore, productivity showed a downfall in 2011-12 and 2012-13. This decreases to 3 efficient firms in 2011-12 and 2 firms in 2012-13. Technological deterioration was the key cause of this regression. In 2013-14, as 4 out of 11 firms had productivity growth it showed a slight improvement. But again it fell to 3 productive firms in 2014-15. Here, the reason can be attributed to both technological regress and efficiency decline. However, productivity further increases in 2015-16 and 8 firms showed productivity growth. It decreases in coming years and there were only 2 productive firms in 2016-17 and 3 in 2017-18. But in 2018-19, it hit 8 productive firms again. The best performance was shown in 2010-11, 2015-16 and 2018-19, when 8 of 11 firms had productivity improvement.

CONCLUSION

It is necessary to analyze the performance of Decision-making units (DMUs) for the proper planning and execution of decisions taken by the management. This paper explores the overall productivity of the Indian Housing firms over the period 2010-2019. The study used the Malmquist Index which is further bifurcated into Technical Efficiency Change (effch) and Technological Change (techch). The effect of Technical change is further classified as Pure Technical Efficiency Change (pech) and Scale Efficiency Change (sech). The study provides complete detail on all of these components. Over the total sample period, based on the results of the Malmquist Index, productivity growth occurred during 2010-11, 2015-16 and 2018-19. The growth was highest in 2015-16, showing productivity gains of 17.1 per cent. The explanation for this can be attributed to technical progress (1.5 per cent) and technological improvement (15.4 per cent). Nevertheless, technological growth had played a significant role. Despite the technical improvement in the past few years, the total factor productivity had declined. This may be due to technical failures as well. Technological progress can be accomplished by optimum utilization of input resources and application of optimum scale level.

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